

A Refined Gibson-Ashby Model for Functionally Graded Honeycombs with Random Irregularities

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Abstract

Honeycomb lattices are widely used as lightweight architected materials, and their mechanical behavior is strongly influenced by unit-cell wall thickness and geometric configuration. Inspired by natural cellular structures, predicting the elastic response of honeycombs with wall-thickness grading and geometric irregularities remains challenging. This study refines the Gibson-Ashby equation for predicting the elastic modulus of honeycombs by introducing two correction factors, κ and η , accounting for functionally graded (FG) wall thickness variations and random irregularities, respectively, i.e., $(\text{relative modulus}) = \kappa\eta C (\text{relative density})^n$. Analytical expressions based on Timoshenko beam theory are extended to FG architectures, providing a stepwise formulation for relative density and elastic modulus variations along the FG direction. This yields a closed-form expression for the effective relative elastic modulus of FG honeycombs, validated by finite element (FE) simulations. Here, κ is calibrated over a broad range of linear and nonlinear wall thickness gradients. Since closed-form formulations for periodic lattices cannot capture random irregularities, η is fitted to an extensive set of FE simulations with random designs. These correction factors are presented as design charts covering hexagonal, square, and triangular honeycombs. Additively manufactured samples produced by 3D printing are tested to validate the predictions and quantify real-world imperfections. This framework provides a direct and computationally efficient means to estimate the elastic modulus of graded and irregular 2D lattices without requiring full numerical homogenization or experiments. The study introduces a unified correction-based approach that bridges analytical cellular-material models with the complexity of natural and fabricated honeycombs.

Keywords: Functionally Graded, Gibson-Ashby Model, Irregular Lattice structures, Porosity, Honeycombs, Additive manufacturing.

1. Introduction

Recent advances in digital and additive manufacturing have significantly expanded the design space for cellular solids, enabling the fabrication of complex architectures with tailored properties [1]. Cellular solids encompass a broad class of engineered porous materials. Honeycombs, a subset of cellular solids, are commonly formed by in-plane repetition of a two-dimensional unit cell with extrusion along the third dimension [2]. Conventional honeycomb designs with hexagonal, triangular, and square unit cells, have been widely studied due to their well-defined periodicity, which simplifies both manufacturing and modeling [3]. However, non-periodic and irregular honeycomb architectures—where structural variations arise from graded wall thickness or random irregularities in unit cell geometry—have received significantly less attention despite their potential advantages. Natural systems, such as bones, frequently exploit both graded and irregular architectures to enhance mechanical efficiency, motivating the exploration of such designs for engineered

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1 structures. Expanding beyond conventional periodic designs allows for optimized honeycombs with superior
2 mechanical performance [4], particularly in lightweight applications such as aerospace and automotive
3 engineering, as well as biomedical applications [5]. Historically, the fabrication of non-periodic structures
4 was constrained by manufacturing limitations, leading to a preference for uniform, periodic honeycombs.
5 However, recent developments in additive manufacturing have overcome these constraints, enabling precise
6 control over spatial variations in geometry and unlocking new opportunities for functional grading (FG) and
7 random irregularity in honeycombs [4, 6].

8 For periodic cellular solids with a well-defined repeating unit cell, the relationship between mechanical
9 properties and relative density can be derived through structural mechanics analysis [7–17]. Under simplified
10 assumptions, the structural analysis may result in a closed-form expression similar to the power-law form of
11 the classical Gibson-Ashby equation [2], where a mechanical property is evaluated as $C \times (\text{relative density})^n$.
12 In such cases, direct comparison with analytical solutions allows for the determination of multiplier C and
13 exponent n . However, when the simplified assumptions in structural mechanics analysis break down—such
14 as in cases where the wall thickness-to-length ratio is large and shear-axial-bending coupling happens and
15 the walls’ overlaps in joints are not ignorable—the analytically derived equations (if exist) may not obey
16 the simplified classical power-law form of the Gibson-Ashby equation. In these scenarios, the classical
17 Gibson-Ashby equation is not able to accurately fit experimental and/or FE simulation results over a wide
18 range of relative densities. Besides, when the structure lacks periodicity, the power-law equation may be
19 empirically fitted to the data to obtain the most suitable values for C and n [18]. In some cases, the classical
20 Gibson-Ashby power-law form fails to provide a reliable best-fit across a broad density range, necessitating
21 modifications to the original form [19].

22 Given the effectiveness of FG microstructures, numerous studies have explored their potential to enhance
23 the mechanical performance of cellular solids. The fundamental concept behind FG design is to introduce a
24 controlled variation in microstructural parameters—such as cell wall thickness, pore size, or bulk material—to
25 achieve optimized mechanical behavior. Compared to repetitive uniform structures, FG configurations offer
26 significant advantages in tailored mechanical responses owing to functional material distribution [20]. Key
27 investigations have demonstrated that FG designs can substantially improve kinetic energy absorption [21–24],
28 reduce initial peak stress under impact loading [25], and enhance buckling collapse [26]. These findings make
29 FG designs highly promising for various engineering applications from graded scaffolds [27–30] to microwave
30 lenses [31].

31 The application of FG cellular solids as structural components, such as beams and plates, has been widely
32 investigated. These studies have demonstrated how a controlled distribution of material along the thickness
33 or length of a structural element can effectively tailor its mechanical response such as stability [32–34], and
34 vibrations [35–38], ultimately leading to optimized structural designs. In such configurations, the mechanical
35 properties vary spatially, making the structure inherently heterogeneous. The foundational approach in most
36 of these studies relies on the Gibson–Ashby equation to establish a relationship between the relative density
37 distribution and the corresponding variations in elastic properties within the structure [39, 40]. However, a
38 review of the literature indicates that in some cases, applying the Gibson–Ashby relation to define property
39 variations within an FG cellular structure, based on spatial coordinates, has led to misunderstandings
40 and misinterpretations by researchers [41]. This highlights the necessity for further investigations into the
41 applicability and limitations of the Gibson–Ashby equation for FG cellular solids, ensuring its accurate use
42 in structural modeling and optimization.

43 These limitations become especially relevant in modern bio-inspired cellular architectures where both FG
44 and geometric irregularity coexist. Cellular architectures that combine functional grading with geometric
45 irregularity are strongly rooted in bio-inspired design. Many natural systems evolve microstructures that vary
46 gradually while incorporating controlled randomness, achieving exceptional mechanical efficiency. Trabecular
47 bone exhibits coordinated density gradients together with inherent microstructural irregularity, enabling
48 local stiffness tuning and load redistribution [42, 43]. Wood and bamboo show stiffness and density gradients
49 along the stem coupled with naturally irregular cellular patterns, providing high bending resistance under
50 multi-axial loading [44]. These biological precedents demonstrate that combining grading and irregularity is
51 an effective and naturally optimized strategy, not an artificial construction. Recent advances in additive
52 manufacturing (AM) now allow engineers to reproduce these coupled natural mechanisms with high fidelity.

1 Modern AM processes can intentionally introduce wall-thickness gradients while simultaneously generating
2 irregularities in geometric, either by design or as controlled manufacturing variations, enabling the fabrication
3 of realistic FG irregular honeycombs.

4 Practical implementations of such structures already appear across several fields. Patient-specific bone
5 scaffolds employ graded and irregular porosity to match the surrounding tissue stiffness, regulate local
6 stress transfer, and promote osseointegration [42]. Protective sports and military helmet liners use FG
7 and controlled irregularity to enhance impact-energy absorption and delay densification; recent studies
8 show that irregularity increases toughness while functional grading manages the transmitted force [45].
9 Automotive crash boxes benefit from tailored wall-thickness distributions that maintain energy-absorption
10 capability even when geometric imperfections are present, improving crashworthiness without increasing mass
11 [46]. Lightweight aerospace components—such as morphing-wing cores and sandwich-panel lattices—use
12 irregular FG microstructures to achieve high out-of-plane stiffness for load bearing while retaining in-plane
13 compliance for morphing, weight reduction, and impact resistance [47]. More recently, graded and irregular
14 honeycomb cores have also been explored in composite crashworthiness components, where they exhibit
15 superior energy-absorption performance compared to uniform honeycombs [48]. These natural inspirations
16 and practical engineered applications demonstrate that FG irregular honeycombs form a relevant and rapidly
17 expanding class of manufacturable structures. The model developed in this work is therefore motivated
18 by both biological evidence and current technological needs, providing a predictive framework capable of
19 accurately capturing the combined effects of grading and irregularity in realistic honeycomb architectures.

20 The study of random irregularities in honeycomb structures has been relatively limited, primarily due to
21 the challenges associated with extending analytical formulations for periodic models to irregular, stochastic
22 architectures. From an experimental standpoint, investigating the effects of random irregularities requires
23 testing a large set of samples to capture the statistical distribution of structural imperfections, which can
24 be costly and time-consuming. FE simulations have been employed as a practical alternative to reduce
25 experimental costs while systematically analyzing the influence of randomness on mechanical properties.
26 Findings indicate that by adjusting the degree of irregularity, it is possible to tailor mechanical performance
27 for a given relative density. This offers a promising avenue for optimizing lattice structures where mechanical
28 behavior can be fine-tuned without altering the overall material volume fraction [21, 49–52].

29 This study directly addresses a critical gap in extending the classical Gibson-Ashby model to FG and
30 randomly irregular honeycombs. A fundamental question in cellular solid design is whether the same
31 power-law exponent n and multiplier C , calibrated for uniform periodic honeycombs, remain valid for FG
32 and irregular architectures. Our findings demonstrate that applying the classical Gibson-Ashby equation
33 without modification leads to significant errors in predicting the elastic modulus of such structures. However,
34 we show that by introducing two correction factors— κ to account for FG variations and η to capture random
35 irregularities—the classical framework can still provide accurate predictions without altering the exponent
36 n . To facilitate practical implementation, κ and η are systematically calibrated through a combination of
37 analytical modeling and extensive FE simulations, covering a wide spectrum of FG profiles (both linear and
38 nonlinear) and degrees of randomness. The results are presented in the form of design charts, for conventional
39 honeycomb designs namely, hexagonal (HEX), triangular (TRI), and square (SQ), offering a straightforward
40 tool for engineers to optimize FG irregular honeycombs while leveraging existing knowledge of uniform
41 periodic architectures. By bridging the gap between theoretical models and real-world applications, this work
42 provides an innovative and practical methodology for integrating FG and irregular lattice structures into
43 advanced structural designs.

44 2. Development of the Model

45 2.1. Defining the geometry of FG honeycombs

46 Three different conventional unit cells have been selected for analysis i.e. HEX, TRI, and SQ [2]. Before
47 introducing any random irregularities, the unit cells are assumed to be regular polygons with equal wall
48 lengths of l , as shown in Fig. 1. Note that for TRI and SQ lattices, the unit cell length is $a = l$ while for
49 HEX it is $a = \sqrt{3}l$.

Figure 1: **Three different unit cells with their geometrical parameters** a) hexagonal (HEX), b) triangular (TRI), and c) square (SQ) unit cell.

1 There are three ways to achieve a graded honeycomb structure. The first is by gradually changing the
 2 properties of the bulk material while keeping the honeycomb geometry unchanged. The second is by gradually
 3 changing the honeycomb wall length, while keeping the bulk material, and wall thickness fixed. The third is
 4 by gradually changing the thickness of the walls while keeping the bulk material, and honeycomb constant
 5 (constant unit cell length) fixed. Here, the third method is chosen because the first method encounters
 6 limitations in multi-material fabrication, while the second method introduces inevitable irregularities in the
 7 honeycomb structure, akin to the variations in pore size observed in irregular foams.

Figure 2: **The schematic of the graded honeycomb structure across FG direction, x .** The dimensionless aspect ratio of the k th unit cell is the average of the aspect ratio of walls at the nodes on both sides.

8 According to Fig. 2, a honeycomb structure with N unit cells of length a , and a total length of $L = Na$
 9 has been assumed in which the thickness of walls located in the i th node between the cells has a certain
 10 thickness of t_i . The dimensionless thickness (aspect ratio) of the wall at the i th node can be defined as
 11 $R_i = t_i/l$. In order to introduce the graded functionality to the honeycomb structure, the aspect ratio can be
 12 changed from R_0 at $x = 0$ to R_N at $x = L$ and the function of gradation is assumed as:

$$R_i = R_0 + \Delta R \left(\frac{i}{N} \right)^m, \quad (1)$$

13 in which $\Delta R = R_N - R_0$, and $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$. Here, the exponent m is chosen to be 1, 2, or 3 to capture
 14 both linear ($m = 1$) and nonlinear ($m \neq 1$) changes in the gradient. This allows for the consideration of
 15 various behaviors associated with the gradation in this study. Next, the average aspect ratio within the k th
 16 cell, \bar{R}_k , is defined by averaging the value of R at the $(k-1)$ th, and k th nodes as,

$$\bar{R}_k = \frac{R_{k-1} + R_k}{2} = R_0 + \frac{\Delta R}{2N^m} ((k-1)^m + k^m), \quad (2)$$

17 where $k = 1, 2, \dots, N$. The elastic modulus of an FG honeycomb can be evaluated based on this step-wise
 18 variation of the aspect ratio through the length.

1 *2.2. Relative density and elastic modulus of honeycombs*

The relative density of a unit cell is a function of its constant aspect ratio, R , i.e., $\rho/\rho_0 = f(R)$, which can be evaluated by summing up the volume of all the walls within the unit cell divided to its total volume. However, the real relative density may be overestimated due to including the overlap part in the walls' joints which is higher for the bigger value of R . Excluding the overlaps in the joints, the exact value of the relative density for the honeycombs with HEX, TRI, and SQ unit cells can be evaluated as follows [53–56]:

$$\left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0}\right)_{HEX} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}}R - \frac{1}{3}R^2, \quad (3a)$$

$$\left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0}\right)_{TRI} = 2\sqrt{3}R - 3R^2, \quad (3b)$$

$$\left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0}\right)_{SQ} = 2R - R^2, \quad (3c)$$

where ρ and ρ_0 are the density of lattice structure and its equivalent bulk material, respectively. Likewise, the relative elastic modulus of the unit cell is a function of its aspect ratio i.e. $E/E_0 = g(R)$. Employing structural analysis based on shear deformable Timoshenko beam theory, the relative elastic modulus for HEX, TRI, and SQ unit cells is calculated as follows [53–56]:

$$\left(\frac{E}{E_0}\right)_{HEX} = \frac{4R^3}{\sqrt{3}} \frac{1}{1 + (5.4 + 1.5\nu_0)R^2}, \quad (4a)$$

$$\left(\frac{E}{E_0}\right)_{TRI} = \frac{2R}{\sqrt{3}} \frac{1 + R^2}{1 + \frac{1}{3}R^2}, \quad (4b)$$

$$\left(\frac{E}{E_0}\right)_{SQ} = R, \quad (4c)$$

where E and ν are the elastic modulus and the Poisson's ratio of the lattice structure and the 0 subscription indicates the equivalent bulk material. The relative density and elastic modulus of a uniform honeycomb with a fixed aspect ratio, R_u , is constant across the whole structure. They can be evaluated by setting $R = R_u$ in Eq. (3) and Eq. (4). By contrast, in the FG honeycombs the aspect ratio R varies from R_0 to R_N according to Eq. (1). It results in a step-wise change along the FG direction, which is the x axis in this study. The relative density, $(\rho/\rho_0)^{(k)}$, of the k th unit cell of an FG honeycomb is calculated by substituting the average aspect ratio, \bar{R}_k , from Eq. (2) to Eq. (3):

$$\left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0}\right)_{HEX}^{(k)} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}}\bar{R}_k - \frac{1}{3}\bar{R}_k^2, \quad (5a)$$

$$\left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0}\right)_{TRI}^{(k)} = 2\sqrt{3}\bar{R}_k - 3\bar{R}_k^2, \quad (5b)$$

$$\left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0}\right)_{SQ}^{(k)} = 2\bar{R}_k - \bar{R}_k^2. \quad (5c)$$

Similarly, the relative elastic modulus, $(E/E_0)^{(k)}$, is obtained by replacing R with \bar{R}_k in Eq. (4):

$$\left(\frac{E}{E_0}\right)_{HEX}^{(k)} = \frac{4\bar{R}_k^3}{\sqrt{3}} \frac{1}{1 + (5.4 + 1.5\nu_0)\bar{R}_k^2}, \quad (6a)$$

$$\left(\frac{E}{E_0}\right)_{TRI}^{(k)} = \frac{2\bar{R}_k}{\sqrt{3}} \frac{1 + \bar{R}_k^2}{1 + \frac{1}{3}\bar{R}_k^2}, \quad (6b)$$

$$\left(\frac{E}{E_0}\right)_{SQ}^{(k)} = \bar{R}_k. \quad (6c)$$

1 *2.3. The approximation function for density and elastic modulus of FG honeycombs*

Since the gradation of the aspect ratio is based on a power law with the exponent m (Eq. (1)), given the values of relative density and elastic modulus of unit cells by Eq. (5) and Eq. (6), one may fit an approximation function of the form $Ax^{\alpha m} + B$ on these values along the FG direction, x , as,

$$P(x) \approx Ax^{\alpha m} + B, \quad (7a)$$

$$A = \frac{P^{(N)} - P^{(1)}}{a^{\alpha m}((N - 0.5)^{\alpha m} - 0.5^{\alpha m})}, \quad (7b)$$

$$B = P^{(1)} - (0.5a)^{\alpha m} A, \quad (7c)$$

2 in which $P(x)$ is either relative density or relative elastic modulus ($\rho(x)/\rho_0$ or $E(x)/E_0$) and α is a calibrated
 3 parameter which can be evaluated by use of curve fitting method, illustrated in Fig. S1 and Fig. S2 in
 4 **Supplementary Information File** for different geometries. The calibrated parameter α has been calculated
 5 for a range of $R_0 < R_N < 0.5$. Note that during the fitting of $P(x)$, the properties of cells are assigned to their
 6 central x -coordinates. Besides, Eq. (7) is fitted so that it exactly passes through the relative properties of the
 7 first ($k = 1$) and the last ($k = N$) unit cell which are evaluated at $x = 0.5a$ and $x = (N - 0.5)a$, respectively.
 8 Given Eq. (7), it is possible to approximate a discontinuous FG honeycomb structure as a continuous graded
 9 medium. Fig. S3 and Fig. S4 in **Supplementary Information File** plot fitted approximation functions,
 10 Eq. (7) for relative density and elastic modulus, by setting $N = 20$ and considering a wide range of variation
 11 in wall aspect ratio, ranging from 0.05 to $R = 0.25$, while the corresponding calibrating parameter, α , is
 12 evaluated from the graphs in Fig. S1 and Fig. S2 in **Supplementary Information File**. Furthermore, to
 13 expand the range of grading variation in aspect ratio, three values of $m = 1, 2$, and 3 are also considered.
 14 Fig. S3 and Fig. S4, confirm the accuracy of the approximated functions introduced in Eq. (7). It is important
 15 to note that the fitting parameter α for the relative modulus of the honeycomb with a SQ unit cell is equal
 16 to 1, as indicated by Eq. (4c).

17 *2.4. The effective properties of FG honeycombs*

18 In the next step of homogenization, the FG honeycombs can be treated as a fully homogeneous medium
 19 by introducing *effective* properties denoted by a bar ($\bar{\cdot}$). The effective density $\bar{\rho}$ can be described as the
 20 density of a fully homogeneous material whose mass is the same as the total mass of FG honeycombs with N
 21 cells while they have an identical apparent volume of $Na hb$ in which hb is the unit cell cross-section area
 22 perpendicular to the FG direction. The effective density can be evaluated as the average of the cells' density:

$$\frac{\bar{\rho}}{\rho_0} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right)^{(k)}. \quad (8)$$

23 However, using the continuous approximation form of the graded relative density, Eq. (7), converts the
 24 summation to an integration form:

$$\frac{\bar{\rho}}{\rho_0} \approx \frac{\int_0^{Na} \left(\frac{\rho(x)}{\rho_0} \right) dx}{Na} = \frac{A(Na)^{(\alpha m)}}{\alpha m + 1} + B. \quad (9)$$

25 The FG honeycombs can be considered as N unit cells with the elastic modulus of $E^{(k)}$, $k = 1, \dots, N$
 26 which are connecting in series. The total elongation of the FG honeycombs under an applied load F_x is:

$$\delta_{graded} = \frac{F_x a}{hb} \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{1}{E^{(k)}}, \quad (10)$$

27 while the elongation of the equivalent fully homogeneous medium with a total length of Na is:

$$\bar{\delta} = \frac{F_x Na}{hb \bar{E}}. \quad (11)$$

1 Comparing Eq. (10) and Eq. (11) one can define the effective relative elastic modulus as:

$$\frac{\bar{E}}{E_0} = \frac{N}{\sum_{k=1}^N \frac{1}{(E/E_0)^{(k)}}}, \quad (12)$$

2 where $(E/E_0)^{(k)}$ is calculated from Eq. (6). Similarly, the integration form related to the continuous
3 approximated expression, Eq. (7), can be written as,

$$\frac{\bar{E}}{E_0} \approx \frac{Na}{\int_0^{Na} \frac{1}{(E(x)/E_0)} dx}. \quad (13)$$

4 Note that replacing Eq. (7) into Eq. (13) may need a numerical integration. The values of effective relative
5 density and effective elastic modulus respectively calculated from Eq. (8) and Eq. (12) have been illustrated
6 in Fig. S5 to Fig. S7 in **Supplementary Information File** for a range of R_0 and R_N .

7 2.5. Definition of random irregularity

8 Various methods for introducing irregularity in honeycomb structures have been discussed in previous
9 literature [21, 51, 52, 57–59]. For the current study, the following equations have been applied to the initial
10 coordinates of each node of the regular configuration $(x_{regular}, y_{regular})$ to find the updated coordinate
11 $(x_{irregular}, y_{irregular})$ corresponding to the irregular structure:

$$\begin{aligned} x_{irregular} &= x_{regular} + \Lambda_1 \Delta l \cos(2\pi \Lambda_2) \\ y_{irregular} &= y_{regular} + \Lambda_1 \Delta l \sin(2\pi \Lambda_2), \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

in which $0 \leq (\Lambda_1 \text{ and } \Lambda_2) \leq 1$ represent random numbers, and Δ defines the degree of irregularity in the

Figure 3: **Definition of random irregularity in honeycombs.** By setting to random parameters, Λ_1 and Λ_2 , the joint node relocates from its location in regular lattice to a random location within a circle of radius Δ (degree of irregularity).

12 honeycomb structure. By applying Eq. (14), each node of the regular structure is randomly relocated within
13 a circle with the radius Δl , as illustrated in Fig. 3. It is noteworthy that $\Delta = 0.5$ is the extreme value of
14 the degree of randomness where there is a chance that some nodes may coincide, resulting in the removal
15 of a wall from a unit cell. To maintain the number of walls in each unit cell, the maximum value of the
16 randomness parameter is changing in the range of $0 \leq \Delta < 0.5$. Fig. 4 illustrates two different degrees of
17 randomness ($\Delta=0.25$ and 0.5) for the honeycombs. The degree of irregularity, denoted as Δ , can influence
18 the elastic modulus, and its impact is incorporated into the modified Gibson-Ashby equation in Section 2.6
19 using the correction factor η .

Figure 4: **Regular and irregular HEX, TRI, and SQ honeycomb structures.** The degree of irregularity is controlled by varying Δ in the degree of 0 to 0.5.

2.6. Modified Gibson-Ashby model for FG irregular honeycombs

The standard Gibson-Ashby equation for a uniform honeycomb can relate the relative density and the relative elastic modulus as follows:

$$\frac{E_u}{E_0} = C \left(\frac{\rho_u}{\rho_0} \right)^n \quad (15)$$

in which C and n are defined as calibration parameters for a uniform honeycomb that should be fitted for a desired configuration. We propose the modified Gibson-Ashby model for FG honeycombs with a random irregularity by substituting Eq. (8) and Eq. (12) into Eq. (15) and introducing κ and η as the correction factors for FG and random irregularity effects, respectively,

$$\frac{\bar{E}}{E_0} = \kappa \eta C \left(\frac{\bar{\rho}}{\rho_0} \right)^n \quad (16)$$

Accordingly, κ is a function f_1 of the degree of gradual changes in the wall thickness, controlled by the ratio (R_N/R_0) and the exponent m , while η is a function f_2 of the degree of randomness, Δ :

$$\kappa = f_1((R_N/R_0), m), \quad (17a)$$

$$\eta = f_2(\Delta), \quad (17b)$$

For the special case of $R_N/R_0 = 1$ or/and $m = 1$, the FG effect disappears, leading to a uniform honeycomb with $\kappa=1$. Besides, $\Delta = 0$ eliminates random irregularity resulting in $\eta=1$. The correction factor κ and η introduced here are later calibrated in Section 4 across a wide range of geometries for HEX, TRI, and SQ honeycombs.

Since the relative properties of the FG honeycombs vary in the gradation direction, x , based on the Eq. (7), it makes sense to define the localized (cell by cell) version of the Gibson-Ashby equation. In order to evaluate the local relative properties, the FG correction factor is set to one ($\kappa=1$) in Eq. (16), because within each cell the aspect ratio is almost uniform. Thus, the localized form is obtained as,

$$\frac{E(x)}{E_0} = \eta C \left(\frac{\rho(x)}{\rho_0} \right)^n \quad (18)$$

2.7. FE simulations

Numerical simulations using FE analysis have been conducted with the aid of the commercial software, COMSOL Multiphysics[®]. Three types of FE models have been utilized as follows:

- **2D beam model:** Each wall is defined as a beam with a rectangular cross-section. The out-of-plane depth is assumed to be equal to the wall length. For uniform configurations, the in-plane beam thickness

1 is set based on the given aspect ratio, R_u , while for the FG honeycombs the beam thickness is defined
 2 as a function of x coordinate (FG direction) so that the aspect ratio varies from the given R_0 and R_N at
 3 two sides with a power of m . For irregular models, the joints are randomly relocated based on Eq. (14).
 4 A unit cell count of $N=20$ along both in-plane directions has been defined to ensure independence
 5 from the number of unit cells, alongside the previous literature [55]. The convergence studies for the
 6 unit cell number have been detailed in Fig. S8 in **Supplementary Information File**. Each beam is
 7 discretized to 10 Timoshenko beam elements with a cubic displacement field and a quadratic rotation
 8 field. Our convergence study confirms that for 10 elements per beam, the calculated relative elastic
 9 modulus accurately converges. A sample meshed model for a uniform TRI geometry is presented in
 10 Fig. S13 in **Supplementary Information File**. This 2D beam model is used for three purposes in
 11 this study: first, the validation study of the model in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7. Second, calibration of the
 12 random irregularity correction factor η , i.e., FE results in Fig. S11 in **Supplementary Information**
 13 **File**. Third, the comparison study for the validity of correction factors, i.e., FEM Beam in Fig. 9. In
 14 the third case, the geometry of the model is identical to the 3D-printed samples while the walls are
 15 modeled as beam elements.

- 16 • **2D plane-stress solid model:** The 2D sketch of CAD models of 3D-printed samples (before extrusion)
 17 are used as the geometry without any modifications. The out-of-plane thickness is set to 10 mm identical
 18 to 3D-printed samples and a plane-stress condition is applied. Models are meshed by a Free triangular
 19 element with a quadratic serendipity displacement field. The convergence study is presented in Fig. S12,
 20 indicating that the calculated relative modulus converges rapidly by increasing the number of elements.
 21 An "extra fine" mesh resolution is applied to all models in COMSOL Multiphysics[®]. A sample meshed
 22 model of an FG-regular HEX geometry is presented in Fig. S13 in **Supplementary Information File**.
 23 The results of this FE model are solely reported in Fig. 9, as FEM Solid 2D, for the comparison study.
- 24 • **3D structural solid model:** The 3D CAD models of 3D-printed samples are used as the geometry
 25 without any modifications. The models are meshed by a Free tetrahedral element with a quadratic
 26 serendipity displacement field. An "extra fine" mesh resolution is applied to all models in COMSOL
 27 Multiphysics[®]. A sample meshed model of an FG-irregular SQ geometry is presented in Fig. S13 in
 28 **Supplementary Information File**. The results of this FE model are solely reported in Fig. 9, as
 29 FEM Solid 3D, for the comparison study.

30 To evaluate the relative elastic modulus of an FE model, we consider two sides of the model perpendicular
 31 to FG direction x . An arbitrary displacement along x is applied to the nodes on one side, while the
 32 displacement of the nodes on the other side is fixed along x direction. In addition, for the 2D beam model,
 33 the rotation of nodes on the fixed side is set to zero. The equivalent stress is determined by dividing the
 34 resultant reaction force along the x direction at the fixed nodes by the apparent cross-sectional area of the
 35 model perpendicular to the load direction. Correspondingly, the equivalent strain is obtained by dividing
 36 the applied displacement by the length of the model along the x direction. Then, the effective modulus is
 37 computed by dividing the equivalent stress by the equivalent strain.

38 3. Method

39 3.1. Fabrication (3D printing) of honeycombs

40 The honeycombs specimens were fabricated using a Stratasys J750[™] 3D printer, operating in high-quality
 41 mode with a layer height resolution of 27 μm and a dimensional accuracy of 200 μm . All specimens were
 42 fabricated using Vero PureBlack[™] material.

43 The mechanical properties of this material were determined through specific uniaxial tests following
 44 ASTM-D638 standards on the dog bone samples shows in Fig. S9. During these auxiliary tests, a constant
 45 strain rate of 0.1 mm/sec was applied to the upper cross-head of the BETA 100 loading frame machine by
 46 MESSPHYSIK. The results yielded an average elastic modulus of $E_0 = 1436 \pm 10$ MPa. Additionally, the
 47 bulk material was estimated to have a density of $\rho_0 = 1.175$ g/cm³.

1 The decision to use a printer that exploits material-jetting technology was made because it allows the
 2 production of almost isotropic samples with relatively small defects [60]. For each unit cell type, three
 3 different configurations were printed namely uniform, FG-regular, and FG-irregular, whose photographs are
 4 presented in Fig. 5. For the uniform samples, the dimensionless thickness was considered to be $R = 0.25$
 5 and the thickness was $t = 2 \pm 0.05$ mm. For FG samples, the degree of gradation, (R_N/R_0) , measured as
 6 2.88, 2.83, and 2.83 for HEX, TRI, and SQ samples, respectively, with a linear variation, i.e., $m=1$. The
 7 corresponding minimum thickness values were $t_0 = 1.35 \pm 0.05$ mm for HEX and SQ and $t_0 = 0.8 \pm .05$ mm
 8 for TRI unit cells.

9 The dimensions of all specimens are measured as 111 ± 0.5 mm \times 88 ± 0.1 mm. To determine the relative
 10 density of the printed samples, accurate weight measurements were taken prior to the compression tests.
 11 The resulting relative densities from weight data have been documented in Table 1 and compared to those
 12 obtained from the CAD models and theoretically predicted by Eq. (8). As seen in Table 1, the 3D-printed
 13 samples present slightly higher relative densities than both CAD and Eq. (8). This systematic increase is
 14 typical of material-jetting 3D printing and is caused by slight over-curing and resin bleed at wall junctions,
 resulting in modestly thicker effective walls than specified in the CAD model [60].

Figure 5: 3D-printed FG specimens for experimental tests. From top to bottom: lattice structures with SQ, TRI, and HEX unit cell, from left to right: uniform, FG regular, and FG irregular.

15

16 3.2. Compression test on 3D-printed honeycombs

17 In order to evaluate the accuracy of the refined Gibson-Ashby model for predicting the relative elastic
 18 modulus of the FG irregular honeycombs, a series of compression tests were conducted on the 3D-printed
 19 honeycombs. The honeycombs were tested under compression load by conducting a steady strain rate of 0.1
 20 mm/sec to the upper face of the specimens with a BETA 100 loading frame machine in order to assess the

Table 1: The relative density ($\bar{\rho} / \rho_0$) computed by weighting the samples and comparing them with the corresponding CAD models and analytical expression in Eq. (8).

		SQ	TRI	HEX
Eq. (8)	Uniform	0.4471	0.6910	0.2742
	FG	0.5520	0.5879	0.3549
CAD Model	Uniform	0.4082	0.5722	0.2407
	FG-Regular	0.4897	0.4871	0.3078
	FG-Irregular	0.5042	0.4905	0.3158
3D-Printed	Uniform	$0.4830 \pm .0242$	$0.6791 \pm .0340$	$0.2863 \pm .0143$
	FG-Regular	0.5813 ± 0.0291	0.5812 ± 0.0291	0.3655 ± 0.0183
	FG-Irregular	0.5990 ± 0.0230	0.5841 ± 0.0292	0.3750 ± 0.0188

1 elastic modulus. Based on the ASTM-D638 guidelines, each configuration of the honeycombs was tested
2 three times. Length changes were measured using a linear variable differential transformer arrangement
3 between the platens to ensure accurate displacement measurement, accounting for frame compliance.

4. Results and discussion

5 This section compares the relative elastic modulus predicted by the proposed modified Gibson-Ashby
6 model, FE numerical simulations, and results obtained from compression tests on the 3D-printed samples.
7 The comparison demonstrates the applicability of the correction factors in capturing the effects of graded
8 wall thickness variation and random irregularities. Firstly, all the fitting parameters in Eq. (16) must be
9 determined. The two parameters, C and n , from the standard form of the Gibson-Ashby equation, i.e.,
10 Eq. (15), are calibrated to the uniform regular honeycombs. To determine these parameters, a range of
11 uniform aspect ratios R_u is introduced into Eq. (3) and Eq. (4) to calculate the relative densities and
12 corresponding relative elastic moduli. For HEX and SQ unit cells $0.05 \leq R_u \leq 0.5$ while for the TRI one,
13 R_u is limited to 0.35 to avoid unrealistically high relative density values. By fitting Eq. (15) to these pairs,
14 values of the multiplier C and the exponent n are determined, as presented in Table 2. Note that Eq. (4)
15 is derived from structural analysis based on Timoshenko beam theory, meaning that the values of C and n are
16 best fitted to this closed-form model.

17 Next, since the analytical relationship for determining the relative elastic modulus, Eq. (4), is based
18 on the assumption of a regular periodic geometry for the honeycombs, the FE model must be utilized to
19 assess the effects of random irregularity and to calibrate the η correction factor. For this purpose, the degree
20 of irregularity is incrementally increased by adjusting the Δ parameter within a range of 0 to 0.5, and its
21 impact on the equivalent elastic modulus of the honeycomb is evaluated via the FE simulations. Due to the
22 random nature of irregularity, 20 random configurations (20 combinations of Λ_1 and Λ_2) are averaged for
23 each value of Δ . The aspect ratio has been consistently maintained at $R_u = 0.25$ across all the models, i.e.,
24 $\kappa=1$, to isolate the effects of irregularity from the graded change in aspect ratio. Fig. S11 in **Supplementary**
25 **Information File** plots the η values that fit the Eq. (16) to the averaged FE results in a given Δ for all
26 three honeycomb types. The results demonstrate that an increase in the Δ results in a dramatic decrease in
27 the relative elastic modulus of honeycombs with SQ and TRI unit cells. For the extreme degree of irregularity
28 with $\Delta=0.5$, the corresponding η values are 0.868 and 0.647, for TRI and SQ honeycombs, respectively,
29 while the HEX unit cell shows almost no clear dependency on irregularity, offering $\eta=1$. It highlights the
30 significant softening effect of random irregularity on TRI and SQ configurations. This is because introducing
31 random irregularities in TRI and SQ lattices alters the deformation mechanism from stretching-dominated
32 to bending-dominated, whereas the HEX design remains bending-dominated regardless of the irregularity.
33 A best-fitting to the observed trend for the SQ and TRI configurations is performed. The fitting function,
34 $\eta = f_2(\Delta)$, is presented in Table 2 for TRI and SQ irregular honeycombs.

1 In the subsequent step, the κ correction factor is fitted for FG honeycombs. To cover a broad spectrum of
 2 grading patterns, the dimensionless wall thickness ratio, (R_N/R_0) , is varied from 1 to 5, while the exponent
 3 m is set to 1, 2, and 3 to account for both linear and nonlinear variations. The effective relative density
 4 and effective relative elastic modulus are evaluated from Eq. (8) and Eq. (12). Substituting these effective
 5 values into Eq. (16), and setting $\eta = 1$ to exclude irregularity, the correction factor κ is obtained across the
 6 range of $1 \leq (R_N/R_0) \leq 5$ for each exponent m . The calibrated κ values for HEX, TRI, and SQ lattices
 7 have been depicted in Fig. S10 in **Supplementary Information File**. In all cases, $\kappa=1$ when $(R_N/R_0)=1$,
 8 corresponding to uniform honeycombs, however, κ gradually decreases by increasing (R_N/R_0) . It means that
 9 the classical Gibson-Ashby equation fitted on uniform honeycombs overestimates the effective relative elastic
 10 modulus for FG ones. HEX honeycombs experience the highest softening due to the FG effect. A best-fitting
 11 for $\kappa = f(R_N/R_0)$ in the form of a quintic function, as presented in Table 2, is performed for each exponent
 12 m . The unknown coefficients are provided in Table S1 in **Supplementary Information File**.

Table 2: The calibrated parameters of the modified Gibson-Ashby model in Eq. (16). The multiplier C and the exponent n are fitted to Eq. (3) and Eq. (4) for uniform honeycombs. The coefficients A_i for estimating the FG correction factor, k , are presented in Table S1 in **Supplementary Information File** for $m=1, 2$, and 3, best fitted to Eq. (8) and Eq. (12). The random irregularity correction factor, η , is fitted to a set of randomly irregular FE simulations for different degrees of irregularity, Δ , as detailed in Fig. S11 in **Supplementary Information File**.

	C	n	$\kappa = f_1((R_N/R_0), m)$	$\eta = f_2(\Delta)$
HEX	0.66	2.43		1
TRI	0.53	1.37	$A_0 + \sum_{p=1}^5 A_p (R_N/R_0)^p$	$1 - 0.53\Delta^{2.01}$
SQ	0.69	1.21		$1 - 0.95\Delta^{1.43}$

13 After calibrating the parameters, C , n , κ , and η , the ability of the modified model proposed in Eq. (16)
 14 to reproduce trends in relative elastic modulus under varying grading and irregularity conditions is examined.
 15 Fig. 6 displays the relationship between the relative elastic modulus and relative density for uniform
 16 honeycombs under both regular ($\Delta=0$) and high-degree irregularity ($\Delta=0.5$) conditions. FE simulations
 17 based on the Timoshenko beam element are provided for both cases. In addition, the analytical expression
 18 from Eq. (5) and Eq. (6) are presented solely for the regular honeycombs. To illustrate the modified
 19 Gibson-Ashby model in Eq. (16), which assumes lattice uniformity ($R_0 = R_N = R_u$), the κ correction factor
 20 is set to 1 while the η correction factor varies depending on the honeycomb type and the degree of irregularity,
 21 indicated by the Δ value. For the regular honeycombs, we set $\eta=1$. The results show an accurate agreement
 22 between the exact expression (hollow circles), and the modified Gibson-Ashby model (solid line), confirming
 23 the accuracy of the calibrated parameters C and n to the closed-form solutions in Eq. (4). Moreover, the FE
 24 simulations for uniform structure (solid red circles) closely follow the modified Gibson-Ashby model (solid line)
 25 with a coefficient of determination, R^2 , equal to 1, 0.99, and 1 for HEX, TRI, and SQ regular honeycombs,
 26 respectively. It confirms the validity of the FE numerical approach. Additionally, for honeycombs with a
 27 high degree of irregularity, Eq. (16) (dashed line) closely matches the FE results for irregular geometries
 28 (solid triangles) across the entire range of aspect ratios, confirming the accuracy of the calibrated η correction
 29 factor. The coefficient of determination, R^2 , is 0.95, 0.99, and 0.96 for HEX, TRI, and SQ irregular uniform
 30 honeycombs, respectively. Note that for HEX uniform lattice solid and dashed lines coincide, since $\eta=1$.

31 Furthermore, to illustrate the impact of irregularity on lattice stiffness, consider the case at a similar
 32 relative density (≈ 0.35). For the regular, uniform structures, the effective stiffness values are approximately
 33 0.052, 0.131, and 0.200 for HEX, TRI, and SQ lattices, respectively (see Fig. 6). Introducing irregularities
 34 reduces these values to 0.047, 0.109, and 0.122, highlighting that HEX lattices are least affected, whereas
 35 TRI and SQ lattices experience more substantial reductions. This trend is consistent with the results shown
 36 in Fig. S11 of the supplementary data.

37 Fig. 7 illustrates the predicted values for the relative elastic modulus for regular and irregular ($\Delta=0.5$)
 38 FG honeycombs for the HEX, TRI, and SQ structures. The FE solutions are presented for both regular
 39 and irregular honeycombs, whereas the analytical solutions are provided only for the regular structures from
 40 Eq. (8) and Eq. (12). The classical Gibson-Ashby equation (Eq. (15) without any correction factor), and the
 41 modified version with the κ correction factor suited to the FG type of honeycomb, detailed in Fig. S10 in

Figure 6: The comparison between the modified Gibson-Ashby model with FE simulations for the uniform regular ($\Delta = 0$) and irregular ($\Delta = 0.5$) honeycombs.

A remarkable accuracy for the calibrated multiplier C and exponent n is observed. The calibrated Gibson-Ashby model accurately fits the FE simulations for both regular and irregular uniform honeycombs.

1 **Supplementary Information File** are also plotted. The corresponding η correction factor is also applied to
2 the irregular honeycomb configurations. Three different cases have been considered for reporting the results:
3 a linear ($m = 1$) gradation with a moderate change in the dimensionless thickness ($R_N/R_0 = 3$), alongside
4 an extreme variation in the dimensionless thickness ($R_N/R_0 = 5$) with linear ($m = 1$) and non-linear ($m = 3$)
5 functionalities.

6 Because the same values of R_0 and R_N produce different relative densities for the three topologies
7 according to Eq. (5), the initial points in Fig. 7 naturally differ between HEX, TRI, and SQ lattices.

8 In all cases, the values of R_0 and R_N are increased proportionally to maintain a constant ratio. For
9 the lattice structures with HEX and SQ unit cells, the minimum and maximum values of the aspect ratio
10 are set to 0.05 and 0.5, respectively, whereas, for the TRI honeycombs, the maximum aspect ratio is set
11 to 0.35. For regular FG honeycombs, the modified model (solid lines) closely fits the analytical expression
12 (hollow circles), confirming the accuracy of the calibrated κ correction factor. Besides, the FE simulations
13 based on the Timoshenko beam element for regular lattices (solid red circles) accurately follow the modified
14 Gibson-Ashby model (solid line) with a coefficient of determination, R^2 , equal to 0.99, 0.82, 0.99 for HEX,
15 0.97, 0.73, and 0.94 for TRI, and 1, 1, and 0.99 for SQ honeycombs for $(m, (R_N/R_0))$ pairs equal to (1,
16 3), (1, 5), and (3, 5), respectively. Comparing the modified model for irregular FG lattices with the FE
17 simulations (solid triangles) illustrated an acceptable accuracy for the model. Although the κ and η correction
18 factors are calibrated independently, the results demonstrate that the proposed modified equation with η
19 correction factor effectively predicts the relative elastic modulus for irregular FG honeycombs across a broad
20 spectrum of aspect ratio variations and high degrees of irregularity. The results obtained from the irregular
21 FG lattice structure with the HEX unit cell align with those of the regular lattice structures, confirming the
22 low sensitivity of the HEX honeycomb to the random irregularity.

23 Next, the accuracy of the localized (cell-by-cell) version of the Gibson-Ashby model introduced in
24 Eq. (18) is examined. For this purpose, both the relative density along the FG honeycomb, $\rho(x)/\rho_0$, and the
25 corresponding relative stiffness values $E(x)/E_0$ are calculated directly from Eq. (7) using the appropriate
26 α parameter provided in Fig. S1 and Fig. S2 in **Supplementary Information File**. Subsequently, the
27 $\rho(x)/\rho_0$ function from Eq. (7) is inserted into Eq. (18) and by incorporating the fitted values of C and n
28 obtained from the curve-fitting on the corresponding uniform honeycomb, presented in Table 2, the value of
29 $E(x)/E_0$ is predicted.

30 Fig. 8 compares the predicted values of the relative elastic modulus using the exact analytical expression
31 and the cell-wise application of the Gibson-Ashby model introduced in Eq. (18). The local density values
32 used along the FG direction correspond to the actual cell positions in the structure, with R_0 and R_N marking
33 in the plots. The results confirm that this pointwise approach effectively captures the variation in elastic
34 modulus with acceptable accuracy across the length of the functionally graded honeycomb.

Figure 7: The Gibson-Ashby model for the uniform regular and irregular ($\Delta = 0.5$) honeycombs with a-c) HEX, d-f) TRI and g-i) SQ unit cell. The correction factors κ and η effectively fit the modified model to the FE simulations and analytical predictions. The classical Gibson-Ashby model is plotted to highlight its significant error in elastic modulus prediction for FG irregular honeycombs.

Figure 8: **The local (cell by cell) Gibson-Ashby model.** Comparison between the exact expression and the Gibson-Ashby models for honeycomb with a-c) HEX, d-f) TRI and g-i) SQ unit cell.

1 Finally, to assess the effectiveness of the correction factors κ and η , nine distinct samples were designed:
2 three uniform, three FG regular, and three FG irregular structures with HEX, TRI, and SQ topologies. These
3 samples were 3D-printed and underwent uniaxial compression tests to determine their relative elastic modulus,
4 as presented in the Methods section. Additionally, the corresponding FE models for these nine designs were
5 constructed based on the exact CAD model of the printed samples. Three different FE approaches were
6 employed: a 3D solid model, a 2D plane-stress solid model, and a Timoshenko beam model, resulting in 27
7 FE simulations in total. Details regarding meshing and boundary conditions are provided in the Methods
8 section. For the given geometric parameters of the samples ($R_N/R_0 = 2.88, 2.83,$ and 2.83 for the HEX,
9 TRI, and SQ designs, respectively, and linear variation in all the samples, $m = 1$), the correction factor κ
10 was found to be 0.67, 0.91, and 0.92 from Table 2. Given the irregularity degree of 0.5 for all the samples,
11 the corresponding values of η were determined as 1.00, 0.87, and 0.66 from Table 2. Since these correction
12 factors act as multipliers for the coefficient C in the Gibson-Ashby equation under a fixed exponent n , we

1 first examined the ratio $C = (E_u/E_0)/(\rho_u/\rho_0)^n$ for the uniform structures. The experimental results from
2 printed samples were compared with predictions from the three FE models (solid 3D, solid 2D plane-stress,
3 and Timoshenko beam) in Fig. 9 (a-c) for HEX, TRI, and SQ configurations. In the uniform case, both κ and
4 η are unity, meaning that these plots directly represent the coefficient C , which establishes the relationship
5 between relative modulus and relative density. The exponent n values are replaced from fitting to analytical
6 expressions in Eq. (3) and Eq. (4) listed in Table 2, along with the relative densities from Table 1. As
7 observed, there are discrepancies among the C values obtained through different methods, indicating that
8 various modeling approaches yield different estimates for the relative modulus. As expected, the FE beam
9 and solid models diverge when the length-to-cross-sectional ratio decreases. The discrepancy between the
10 experimental and modeled results arises from multiple factors. First, as shown in Table 1, the theoretical
11 predictions for relative densities by Eq. (8) exhibit lower relative densities than printed specimens. Second,
12 the Gibson-Ashby model, while effective for low-density cellular structures, becomes less accurate at higher
13 relative densities (0.29–0.68 for 3D-printed samples), as widely documented in the literature. This limitation
14 is inherent to the model itself. Third, the correction factors κ and η are fitted to a wide range of FG and
15 irregular designs where a certain level of deviation in every fitting is unavoidable. Lastly, variability in the
16 bulk material properties, particularly in 3D-printed polymers, contributes to deviations. The elastic modulus
17 of the bulk material may differ when printed as a solid block in dogbone samples versus thin honeycomb walls
18 due to differences in solidification conditions and defect formation. Thus, using the bulk elastic modulus from
19 a printed solid reference sample as the denominator in relative modulus calculations introduces additional
20 uncertainty.

21 Despite variations in C values for different methods in Fig. 9 (a-c), it is essential to clarify that the
22 goal of this study is not to tune C to fit the Gibson-Ashby model to experimental data. Instead, our
23 objective is to assess whether the analytically derived κ and numerically determined η , based on Timoshenko
24 beam simulations, can reliably capture the effects of FG and random irregularities in both experimental
25 and solid FE models. To evaluate this, the corresponding correction factors were applied to experimental
26 and numerical results in Fig. 9 (d-i) for HEX, TRI, and SQ structures. The results demonstrate that
27 introducing FG architectures and random irregularities consistently reduces the proportionality coefficient in
28 the Gibson-Ashby equation, aligning with our model’s predictions, where both κ and η are less than unity. As
29 expected, since these correction factors were calibrated based on Timoshenko beam theory, they accurately
30 predict these effects in beam-based FE models with a maximum error of 6%. Notably, the same correction
31 factors also provide reasonable predictions for 3D-printed samples, with a prediction error below 15%.

32 This normalized validation format was deliberately chosen because it removes secondary experimental
33 variability (bulk modulus, density measurement) and directly proves that the proposed κ and η factors
34 accurately extend the classical uniform C value to real graded and irregular lattices.

35 Therefore, it is proved that the proposed correction framework serves as a practical tool for incorporating
36 FG architectures and random irregularities in cases where the uniform Gibson-Ashby coefficient C is available.
37 For denser honeycombs, where the standard Gibson–Ashby model tends to underestimate stiffness, the
38 revised formulations by [61] offer improved predictions. While our study primarily focuses on the effect of
39 functional grading and irregularities, incorporating their correction could further enhance accuracy in the
40 high-density regime and will be considered in future work.

41 The proposed κ and η correction framework suggests three main advantages. First, it preserves the
42 conventional Gibson–Ashby power-law form and keeps the standard C and n values used for regular
43 honeycombs, so existing material databases can be used without re-calibration. Second, the correction factors
44 are provided as ready-to-use charts that eliminate the need for additional simulations or experiments. Third,
45 the method improves stiffness prediction for both beam-based models and real 3D-printed specimens, even in
46 cases with strong grading or pronounced irregularities, and its accuracy is suitable for preliminary design
47 and certification. The main limitation is that the current charts apply only to in-plane elastic modulus
48 of extruded 2D honeycombs loaded along the grading direction; out-of-plane loading and fully 3D lattice
49 architectures require separate calibration. The approach is directly applicable to additively manufactured
50 aerospace sandwich cores, automotive energy-absorbing structures, biomedical scaffolds, and lightweight
51 protective gear, where fast and reliable stiffness estimation of imperfect graded lattices is essential for design
52 optimization and certification workflows.

Figure 9: The validation study of correction factors in predicting the FG and irregularity effects on the relative elastic modulus of honeycombs. a-c) The multiple C values that fit the elastic modulus of 3D-printed and different FE simulations to the Gibson-Ashby model. d-f) The comparison study for the accuracy of the κ correction factor for FG-regular honeycombs. g-i) The comparison study for the accuracy of the η correction factor for FG-irregular honeycombs. Percentage errors are calculated as $100 \times |C_{\text{eff,predicted}} - C_{\text{eff,measured}}|/C_{\text{eff,measured}}$. Using this normalized form isolates the performance of the correction factors from scatter in bulk modulus and measured density, directly demonstrating that κ and η act as universal multipliers on the classical uniform C .

1 5. Conclusion

2 In this study, a modified model for predicting the elastic modulus of irregular FG honeycombs was
3 developed by incorporating two correction factors into the classical Gibson-Ashby equation. These factors
4 account for the gradual variation in wall thickness (κ) and random structural irregularities (η). Analytical
5 approaches and FE simulations based on the Timoshenko beam theory were employed to determine these
6 correction factors, and the accuracy of the model was validated against experimental tests on 3D-printed
7 specimens. The results indicate that both functional grading and structural randomness lead to a reduction
8 in the relative elastic modulus compared to uniform, periodic geometries, which are reflected in correction
9 factors smaller than unity. More importantly, the proposed correction coefficients, although derived using the
10 Timoshenko beam model, successfully captured the FG and irregularity effects in 3D-printed samples with a
11 maximum error of 14.8% in experimentally measured relative elastic modulus of FG irregular samples. This
12 highlights the effectiveness of the proposed correction framework in estimating the impact of randomness and
13 FG variations in honeycombs by applying proper correction factors to a known uniform honeycomb modulus.

14 One of the key challenges in utilizing classical models such as Gibson-Ashby is their assumption of ideal,
15 periodic structures, whereas real-world cellular materials often exhibit FG variations and irregularities. The
16 proposed modified model bridges this gap by enabling rapid and accurate estimation of the elastic modulus
17 without requiring extensive computational simulations or experimental testing. The proposed framework
18 can be applied in optimizing honeycomb designs for engineering applications such as biomedical implants,
19 impact absorption, and lightweight structures. For instance, in biomaterials, precise stiffness control in
20 porous implants is crucial for improving mechanical compatibility with bone. Our model allows designers to
21 estimate the effects of FG and irregularities on elastic modulus without expensive trial-and-error experiments.
22 Although FE modeling is commonly used, this study provides a systematic approach to evaluate the combined
23 effects of functional grading and structural irregularities on stiffness, which is less explored in the current
24 literature. Additionally, in aerospace and automotive industries, where lightweight yet robust structures
25 are essential, this model offers a flexible and efficient framework for early-stage evaluation of mechanical
26 performance in functionally graded cellular structures. Overall, this study provides a practical tool for
27 estimating the elastic modulus of complex cellular materials.

1 **6. Author contributions statement**

2 M.J.B. conducted the software implementation and managed data curation. S.K.J. performed the formal
3 analysis. Both M.J.B and S.K.J. were involved in the investigation, validation, and preparation of the original
4 draft. D.M. and N.M.P. supervised, provided resources, and funding acquisition . All authors contributed to
5 the conceptualization, methodology, and review & editing of the manuscript.

6 **7. Declaration of Interest**

7 The authors declare no competing interests.

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